

A CASE STUDY ON THE DETERMINANTS OF COACHING CULTURE DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT

It is the purpose of this paper to investigate how factors related to the development of a coaching culture interact. Surveys of 110 people from Mahindra & Mahindra, Chakan, Pune, were conducted as part of the quantitative research design (descriptive). Researchers found a strong correlation between the development of a coaching culture and all five of the study's determinants (manager commitment, link between business strategy and development focus, recognition and reward of coaching culture behaviours, training for coaches, and opportunities for learning and development). Significantly, the availability of opportunities for professional growth and development had a larger role in the creation of this coaching culture.

Keywords: coaching culture, manager commitment, business, learning and development

1. Introduction

Coaching may be a useful tool for both organisations and individuals in today's globalised environment. As a result of good coaching, an organisation may be able to adapt more quickly to changes in its environment (Redshaw, 2000). Management, as indicated by Redshaw in his article, must play a role in helping individuals achieve their maximum potential. Additionally, coaching may help companies create long-term gains through enhancing performance at the individual, group and organisation levels. As a consequence of these ongoing improvements, employees' knowledge, skills, and capacities will increase. An employee's performance in the context of coaching may be described as "coaxed" (Armstrong, M. and Baron, A. 2004). Individuals and organisations benefit from the coaching process because it promotes lifelong learning, fosters innovation, improves problem-solving skills, and fosters a never-ending quest for betterment (Hafford-Letchfield, 2007). It has also been observed that an organization's coaching culture is crucial, showing that the move from traditional work style to more current one that supports autonomy may result in an increased feeling of responsibility for employees' achievement. As long as there is no motivation for their employees or management, they won't be able to achieve their goals. Mahindra & Mahindra's new world-class manufacturing plant at Chakan, near Pune, is the subject of this study,

which investigates the connection between numerous elements. When it comes to training and development for new employees, the use of coaching is an integral aspect of the company's culture. An important component of the solution is identifying and rewarding coaching culture behaviours and providing coaches with adequate training and opportunities for advancement. Mahindra & Mahindra Plant in Chakan, Pune conducted a survey of 110 employees to obtain information on coaching culture and determine the variables that lead to the creation of a coaching culture. Mahindra Group Vice Chairman and Managing Director Anand Mahindra, M&M; Ltd. President Pawan Goenka, Maharashtra Chief Minister Ashok Chavan, and other prominent dignitaries were in attendance when the new facility was launched on March 13, 2010 by the Maharashtra Chief Minister Ashok Chavan. Located on 700 acres of land at an estimated cost of \$1 billion, the factory is one of India's biggest green field projects. There is an increasing awareness that coaching can be used to develop leaders. In this context, coaches may take on the same role as mentors. Like mentors, coaches will often use a mix of "technical advice" and "personal feedback" to with others. To be effective, the coach should have the characteristics described above for effective leaders.

The perception that coaching is a response to employee problems is not entirely correct. Coaching is beneficial because it focuses on developing individual employees. This focus

can help organisations increase their competitiveness, productivity, cash flow, customer satisfaction, market share and market penetration because the organisation fosters high levels of employee retention.

Aligned with the business strategy, many aspects that are required for generating a coaching culture are considered by the company. This includes recognition and reward of coaching culture behaviours, coach training and development opportunities, the relationship between business strategy and developmental focus on coaching culture behaviours, managers' willingness to support the development of a coaching culture, mentoring programs for new hires.

The coach's job is to help employees reach their goals. To do this, the coach will need to take time to understand the employee's job and career path. The coach should believe that coaching can be used to develop leaders and will therefore encourage employees to become more involved in the organisation. Leaders should also make sure that their employees are aware of the goals they are trying to achieve and demonstrate how these goals will strengthen employee commitment.

Mentoring is an effective teaching method that can be used in coaching. In this mentoring activity, a coach can serve as a mentor to their employees. In this approach, the coach will provide guidance to the employees in a non-evaluative way. This type of coaching is useful for training and developing individuals, because it provides "intensive feedback." This process also helps employees become more inspired and committed to achieving their goals.

One of the most important steps in creating a coaching culture is encouraging managers to support it. In many situations, managers have been found to have a significant influence on employees. In this case, managers should consider coaching as a technique that will help employees to feel more committed to the organisation as well as improve its financial health. By supporting coaching, managers can develop a "sense of ownership" and improve the performance of their employees.

It is equally important for leaders and managers to recognize and reward members who demonstrate coaching culture behaviours.

This recognition and rewards will encourage other individuals in the organisation to create and support a coaching culture.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Coaching Models

According to Anderson, Frankovelgia, and Broome, "coaching is a procedure to develop the relationship that has been built up by management" (2009). This will lead to greater team efficiency, which will in turn improve the ability to carry out business strategy, as stated by the authors (Anderson et.al., 2009). A high-performance culture may be created in an organisation by using Thompson, G. (2007)'s GROW model. Three guiding themes may be used to determine the effectiveness of coaching partnerships. One must first earn the right to serve as a coach by building trusting connections with his or her colleagues. A ideal relationship occurs when a coach utilises their expertise to enhance the talents of the people they work with, motivates them, and takes responsibility for them to perform at their utmost best. The third and last guideline is to refrain from engaging in pointless debates. By Whitmore, J. (2002), communication enhances all aspect of a person's personal and professional life at the same time, a basic component of human connections. It has also been used by managers in the company to help them strengthen their coaching skills. In 2002, Whitmore, J., created a set of guidelines for managers to follow. Human potential may be enhanced via the use of coaching as stated by McMahan G. (2002). Workers and managers benefit from greater productivity and a solid working relationship when coaching is an integral element of the company's culture. As a result, a new seven-step coaching model was created to offer an overview of the abilities and approaches that a coach might utilise to attain this GROW model. In the first step, each employee's personal and professional life is thoroughly analysed by the coaches. According to Dembkowski and Eldridge, it is essential to acquire coaching skills in order to establish a feeling of community among employees (2003).

2.2. Influences on Creating an Organizational Culture for Coaching

An organization's values, standards, and beliefs may be utilised as a guide to assist it adapt to its new environment, according to a variety of authors. Management team members should be engaged in brainstorming about how coaching might improve the long-term goals of the firm. Management team members need to be able to see how their extended goals affect them. As a consequence of this knowledge, people have a better understanding of coaching and how to use it to enhance their performance and fulfil their goals. In order to motivate and inspire their employees to reach their goals, managers must first discover the unique learning styles of each member of their staff. According to Anderson et.al.(2009), companies should ask their employees what sort of culture they like in order to achieve their objectives. Absent a firm commitment from the top as well as an encouraging corporate culture, even the best-laid plans will fail. When developing a coaching culture in a firm, it is critical to recognise and reward the behaviours that contribute to this culture. Many successful businesses make a concerted effort to cultivate an information-sharing culture (Lewicka, 2011). People in middle management who often feel isolated or helpless will find this motivating as it shows that they have access to the top echelons of company. Coaches and trainees will be pleased if their efforts are recognised or rewarded by their employers (Clutterbuck & Megginson, 2005). When an organisation delivers coaching training to a pool of coaches, the culture of the organisation is established. The advantages of recognising line manager coaches' competence and performance in the role might be debated. The line manager must attend both the first and supplementary training sessions.... Coaches would be able to observe them while they worked out. An organisation with a coaching culture is one that provides managers with opportunities to learn how to coach via training and follow-up coaching sessions with an external, experienced coach (Whitaker, 2009). The first step in becoming a coach is to get a thorough awareness of the role coaching plays within an organization's overall strategy.

3. Methodology

The study focused on the development of a coaching culture and all five of the study's determinants.

110 workers were chosen for the purpose of the study, using convenience sampling. (The employees were selected from: Mahindra & Mahindra, since this is a case study)

The researcher designed and validated a 10-point each questionnaire for assessing the impact of coaching culture development on:

- a. manager commitment,
- b. link between business strategy and development focus,
- c. recognition and reward of coaching culture behaviours,
- d. training for coaches, and
- e. opportunities for learning and development

Checked the questionnaire for validity using Cronbach's Alpha.

Seek responses on a 5-point Likert Scale to gauge the level of Significance (From "no significance at all" influential to maximum significance)

Conducted the survey

Summarized the responses, and analysed the results

Hypotheses

H1: Manager commitment, has significant relationship in creating a coaching culture

H2: Link between business strategy and development focus, has significant relationship in creating a coaching culture

H3: Recognition and reward of coaching culture behaviours, has significant relationship in creating a coaching culture

H4: Training for coaches, has significant relationship in creating a coaching culture

H5: Opportunities for learning and development has significant relationship in creating a coaching culture

Scheme formed for testing of hypotheses

1. Responses were collected under 6 sections:

- a. Profile Information
- b. Manager commitment,
- c. Link between business strategy and development focus,
- d. Recognition and reward of coaching culture behaviours,
- e. Training for coaches, and

- f. Opportunities for learning and development
2. The Likert responses were considered for calculating the mean values and correlation analysis was used.
 3. Since the researcher has used non-parametric data for a parametric test (One Sample T test), a more stringent alpha level of 0.01 was chosen (Murray, 2013).
 4. In order to check the internal validity of the questionnaires, Cronbach alpha values were calculated.

4. Results

1. Firstly, the Cronbach’s Alpha values were calculated for the 5 items under consideration. Following were the results:
- 2.

Table 1. Item	Reliability Statistics	
	Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
Manager commitment,	.811	10
Link between business strategy and development focus,	.784	10
Recognition and reward of coaching culture behaviours,	.801	10
Training for coaches, and	.771	10
Opportunities for learning and development	.769	10

The above table shows that the Cronbach alpha values for all the sections was over 0.7. This displays internal consistency and validity of the questionnaire.

5. Findings and Discussion

At a significance level of p0.01 (Table 1), all of the five coaching culture factors were shown to positively correlate with each other. Manager commitment (r=0.46), the relationship between company strategy and development emphasis (r=0.40), the recognition and reward of coaching culture behaviours (r=0.40), and training for coaches (r=0.30) are the four determinants. To create a coaching culture, only learning and development opportunities were shown to have a favourable correlation with (r=0.50).

Table 2: Correlation between determinants in creating a coaching culture

Determinants	In Creating a
Manager Commitment	.332*
Link between business	.401*
Recognize and reward	.338*
Training for coaches	.387*
Learning and development	.617*

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (1-tailed); ** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (1-tailed)

There is a strong correlation between every factor that has been studied when it comes to developing a coaching culture. Clutterbuck & Megginson's support of a coaching culture is directly related to the dedication of managers in their organisations (2005). One of the most important components in developing a coaching culture is the connection between corporate strategy and development emphasis. Many of those polled agreed that it is critical. Coaching culture behaviours that are recognised and rewarded have a substantial impact on the development of a coaching culture. It is critical to encourage coaching culture-aligned behaviours by engaging in communications and rewards activities as employee behaviour shifts. Once a business has implemented a coaching culture, it must be actively and creatively disseminated across the organisation (Anderson et.al., 2005). Organizations will make errors if they provide training and coaching for managers without limiting the quality of coaches they use in the process of developing a coaching culture. It's because managers just do what's required of them. Organizations may begin implementing a coaching effort if they have confidence in the quality of their coaches. At a significant level of p0.01, only the learning and development opportunities mentioned have an important association to the growth of coaching (r=0.617). In order to foster a coaching culture, Whitaker (2009) said that providing employees with chances for learning and growth will inevitably improve their performance. The first step in becoming a skilled coach is to have an understanding of what coaching is and how it fits into an organization's overall plan. Figure 1 summarises Pearson's correlation findings for factors that contribute to the development of a coaching culture.

6. Conclusion

In the 21st century, the rivalry between businesses is essentially a fight for human resources. One of the most essential factors in encouraging workers to put in extra effort and achieve higher levels of job performance is a supportive work environment. As a result of this study, managers' willingness to support the development of a coaching culture, the relationship between business strategy and developmental focus on coaching culture behaviours, the recognition and reward of coaching culture behaviours, coach training and development opportunities all play a role.

However, creating a coaching culture is somewhat more than just adopting a new set of leadership beliefs and behaviours. Instead, it requires organisations to adopt new practices that reflect the importance of coaching. This can be achieved by utilising coaching for business strategy purposes or any annual goals proposed by the company leaders. The company leaders should also ensure that their employees are aware of the goals they are trying to achieve and demonstrate how they will benefit the employees if they achieve their goals.

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